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**CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN THE INTEGRATION OF
INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE SYSTEMS AND PRACTICES INTO THE
CURRICULUM: A NARRATIVE INQUIRY**

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ABSTRACT

Indigenous Peoples' Education (IPEd) has gained recognition worldwide as a means to empower Indigenous communities, promote cultural preservation, and enhance educational outcomes. This study explored the challenges and opportunities in integrating Indigenous Knowledge Systems (IKS) and traditional wisdom into the curriculum of Indigenous education programs in DepEd Esperanza III, Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2024-2025. Using a qualitative research design and narrative inquiry approach, fifteen teachers from selected Indigenous Peoples (IP) schools participated in semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions. Thematic analysis was employed to analyze the data. Results revealed that developing culturally relevant curriculum materials incorporating IKS presents both challenges and opportunities. Key challenges include the need for culturally sensitive materials, difficulties accessing skilled personnel, and issues related to language barriers and translation. Balancing curriculum standardization with the flexibility required to integrate IKS was also identified as a challenge. Opportunities, however, emerged through community engagement, collaboration with elders, and teacher training initiatives to ensure cultural authenticity in materials and teaching practices. The study highlighted that integrating IKS into the curriculum requires a multifaceted approach involving contextualization, cultural sensitivity, language preservation, and community collaboration. This approach not only ensures academic rigor but also empowers students to preserve their heritage. Teachers, despite facing resource limitations and insufficient support, demonstrated commitment to authentic IKS integration through collaboration with elders and continuous professional development. The integration of IKS has profound impacts on students' cultural identity, academic achievement, and emotional well-being. By connecting students to their heritage and fostering academic success, IKS integration provides a holistic educational experience that strengthens students' sense of self. Recommendations include allocating funds for culturally sensitive curriculum materials, promoting teacher training, and strengthening partnerships with Indigenous communities to ensure the successful integration of IKS in education.

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Keywords: Indigenous Knowledge Systems, Curriculum Integration, Narrative Inquiry, Cultural Education, & Educational Challenges and Opportunities

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Indigenous Peoples' Education (IPEd) has gained recognition worldwide as a means to empower Indigenous communities, promote cultural preservation, and enhance educational outcomes. A critical aspect of IPEd involves integrating Indigenous Knowledge Systems (IKS) and traditional wisdom into the curriculum.

Indigenous Knowledge Systems encompass a rich repository of traditional wisdom, passed down through generations, and deeply rooted in Indigenous cultures. These systems include knowledge about the environment, natural resources, social structures, healing practices, and spirituality. Integrating IKS into the curriculum of Indigenous schools holds the potential to enhance cultural identity, improve learning outcomes, and empower Indigenous communities (Battiste, 2013; Cajete, 1999).

While there is a growing recognition of the importance of IKS in education, several gaps persist in the literature and practice. There is a scarcity of empirical research that systematically explores the integration of IKS into the curriculum within the context of Indigenous education programs. Further, the development of culturally relevant curriculum materials that effectively incorporate IKS remains an ongoing challenge, requiring further exploration.

Furthermore, The readiness and capacity of teachers to integrate IKS into their teaching practices and effectively transmit traditional wisdom require in-depth investigation. Also, strategies for assessing the impact of IKS integration on students' cultural identity, academic achievement, and overall well-being are underdeveloped (Magonsik & Ngag, 2025).

This study seeks to address these research questions through a comprehensive examination of the integration of traditional wisdom and Indigenous knowledge into the curriculum of Indigenous education programs, ultimately contributing to the advancement of culturally inclusive and empowering education for Indigenous Peoples.

Research Questions

This study explored the challenges and opportunities in the integration of traditional wisdom and Indigenous knowledge into the curriculum of Indigenous education programs in Esperanza III, division of Sultan Kudarat during school year 2024-2025.

Specifically, this sought to answer the following:

1. What challenges and opportunities are encountered in the development of culturally relevant curriculum materials that incorporate IKS?

1. How is Indigenous Knowledge Systems (IKS) integrated into the curriculum of Indigenous education programs in DepEd Esperanza III?

3. How do teachers in Indigenous schools perceive their preparedness and capacity to integrate IKS into their teaching practices?

4. What are the potential impacts of IKS integration on students' cultural identity, academic achievement, and overall well-being within Indigenous education programs?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research design, particularly narrative inquiry to investigate the challenges and opportunities in the integration of traditional wisdom and Indigenous knowledge into the curriculum of Indigenous education programs in Esperanza III, division of Sultan Kudarat during school year 2024-2025.

Narrative inquiry is a qualitative research method that focuses on the study of individuals' lived experiences as told through their personal stories. It emphasizes the way people create meaning in their lives through narratives, which are considered both a method of communication and a mode of knowing. In narrative inquiry, researchers collect and analyze these stories to gain insights into the participants' perspectives, cultural contexts, and the processes through which they construct their identities and make sense of their experiences (Clandinin and Connelly, 2000).

Participants of the Study

Table 1 displays the qualification of the participants based on the criteria set by the researcher prior to the selection of qualified informants of the study.

Table 1

Participants' Inclusion Criteria

Qualifications
<i>Participants: 15 Teachers</i>
1. Experience in Teaching Indigenous Learners Teachers must have at least two years of experience teaching Indigenous learners in DepEd Esperanza III.
2. Involvement in Curriculum Development or Implementation Teachers should have been involved in either the development or implementation of curriculum that incorporates Indigenous knowledge systems and practices.
3. Willingness to Share Personal Experiences Teachers must be willing to participate in a narrative inquiry and share detailed personal experiences regarding the integration of Indigenous knowledge.

4. Demonstrated Understanding of Indigenous Knowledge

Teachers should demonstrate a basic understanding of Indigenous knowledge systems and practices, either through formal training, workshops, or community engagement.

The participants of this study were the selected fifteen (15) teachers assigned in IP schools in DepEd Esperanza III division of Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2024-2025, who qualify the inclusion criteria set by the researcher.

Sampling Technique

This study employed a Purposive Sampling Technique to purposefully select fifteen (15) teachers in DepEd Esperanza III division of Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2024-2025. Purposive sampling, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their own discretion when selecting population members to participate in their surveys (Alchemer, 2021) as also cited by Ngag (2023)..

This survey sampling method necessitates that researchers have prior knowledge of the purpose of their studies in order to select and approach eligible participants for online survey platforms such as Alchemer. Researchers use purposive sampling to gain access to a specific subset of individuals, as all survey respondents are chosen because they suit a specific profile.

Locale of the Study

This research was conducted in the selected IP elementary and integrated schools in Esperanza III, division of Sultan Kudarat for the school year 2024-2025. See google map below:

Research Instruments

A semi-structured interview was utilized in this study as an exploratory tool to be used during the interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) to explore data regarding the challenges and opportunities in the integration of traditional wisdom and Indigenous knowledge into the curriculum of Indigenous education programs in Esperanza III, division of Sultan Kudarat during school year 2024-2025. This instrument was validated by the panel of evaluators who are experts in the construction of relevant instruments.

Data Gathering Procedure

The study's reliability was ensured by the researcher's strict adherence to a set of protocols. The study's focus was to explore the challenges and opportunities in the integration of traditional wisdom and Indigenous knowledge into the curriculum of Indigenous education programs in Esperanza III, Division of Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2024-2025.

First, the Superintendent of DepEd-Sultan Kudarat and the Dean of the CGS were

requested to sign a document authorizing the researcher to take the necessary steps to conduct the study.

A second authorization letter was sent to the District Supervisor of DepEd Esperanza III to acquire the precise data necessary for this study. A survey questionnaire/interview protocol was created, evaluated, and implemented.

The researcher then chose respondents using a Purposive Sampling Technique, considering all the newly appointed school heads to be the participants of the study. As long as health procedures were adhered to, the researcher began distributing the interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) via face-to-face mode.

Finally, the data acquired from the interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were collated, analyzed, and interpreted using thematic analysis.

Data Transcription Process

All gathered raw data from the participants through interview and FGD were transcribed using the transcription process of Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). By following these step-by-step processes, the researcher aligned their transcription approach with the guidelines outlined by Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). This rigorous transcription process ensured the trustworthiness and credibility of the qualitative data, which served as the foundation for the subsequent narrative analysis and the meaningful interpretation of the gathered raw data (Ngag, 2023).

In the context of the study on the challenges and opportunities in the integration of traditional wisdom and Indigenous knowledge into the curriculum of Indigenous education programs in Esperanza III, Division of Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2024-2025, the steps in the transcription process were outlined as follows:

Step1: Audio Recording of Interviews: The first step in the transcription process involved audio recording interviews with the participants. For this study, the researcher conducted in-depth interviews with the teachers in Esperanza District, Division of Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2024-2025. These interviews were recorded with explicit consent from the participants.

Step 2: Verbatim Transcription: Verbatim transcription was crucial as it captured participants' responses exactly as spoken, including pauses, hesitations, and emotional expressions. The researcher meticulously transcribed the audio recordings, ensuring to preserve the precise language, grammatical structures, and speech patterns of the participants interviewed.

Step 3: Researcher Verification: After transcription, the researcher verified the accuracy of transcripts by carefully reviewing them for any discrepancies or omissions. This step ensured that the written text faithfully represented the original audio recordings and maintained the integrity of the data collected.

Step 4: Participant Validation: Following transcription, the researcher shared the transcripts with participants for their review and feedback. Participants had the opportunity to validate the accuracy of their recorded responses, providing insights or clarifications where

necessary. This process ensured that participants' perspectives were accurately represented in the study.

Step 5: Anonymization: To protect participants' confidentiality, the researcher anonymized transcripts by replacing any identifying information, such as names or specific locations, with pseudonyms or generic descriptors. This precautionary measure safeguarded the privacy of the young learners involved in the study.

Data Analysis

A thematic or content analysis was used to analyze and analyse the data. By assigning each text's assertions, phrases, and words to a system or collection of categories—either based on or adapted from existing ones or established from scratch in connection to the study objectives (Clark and Braun, 2006).

Written interview data was collected from the participants to determine the challenges and opportunities in the integration of traditional wisdom and Indigenous knowledge into the curriculum of Indigenous education programs in Esperanza III, division of Sultan Kudarat during school year 2024-2025.

The interviews and FGDs conducted for this research were used to distill the most salient participant answers into overarching themes.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study focused on exploring the challenges and opportunities involved in integrating Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSP) into the curriculum in the schools of Esperanza III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, during the school year 2024-2025. The research specifically examined the experiences of teachers, school administrators, and curriculum developers in the district as they worked to incorporate IKSP into educational content. The study aimed to understand the cultural relevance, pedagogical adjustments, and community engagement involved in this integration process. The narrative inquiry approach allowed for a deep exploration of the personal and professional stories of those involved in implementing IKSP in the educational setting.

The study was delimited to the schools in the Esperanza III district within the Division of Sultan Kudarat, focusing exclusively on the integration of IKSP into the curriculum during the 2024-2025 school year. It did not cover the broader provincial or national context beyond this district, nor did it explore other educational reforms or curricular changes unrelated to IKSP.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Results show that the Developing culturally relevant curriculum materials that incorporate Indigenous Knowledge Systems (IKS) presents both challenges and opportunities. Key challenges include the need for culturally sensitive materials that respect Indigenous norms, values, and traditions, alongside difficulties in accessing skilled personnel, funding, and authentic resources. Language barriers and translation issues can also lead to misinterpretation or exclusion of IKS, while balancing curriculum standardization with the flexibility needed to integrate IKS

effectively remains a challenge. However, opportunities arise through community engagement and collaboration with elders, ensuring accuracy and cultural authenticity, as well as the importance of teacher training and capacity building to support the development and implementation of culturally sensitive materials.

Further, the integration of Indigenous Knowledge Systems (IKS) into the curriculum of Indigenous Education Programs in DepEd Esperanza III involves a multifaceted approach that includes contextualization, cultural sensitivity, language preservation, community collaboration, and the use of localized materials. These strategies ensure that indigenous students receive an education that is both academically rigorous and culturally relevant, empowering them to preserve their heritage while thriving in a modern educational environment. By incorporating these elements, DepEd Esperanza III demonstrates its commitment to providing an inclusive, equitable, and culturally responsive education that values and respects the knowledge and traditions of indigenous communities.

Furthermore, while teachers in Indigenous schools in DepEd Esperanza III recognize the importance of integrating IKS into their teaching practices, they face various challenges and barriers, including insufficient resources, limited support, and the need for more professional development. However, the themes identified in this study highlight the teachers' commitment to integrating IKS authentically, through collaboration with indigenous elders, ongoing training, and a strong sense of responsibility for preserving cultural authenticity. As research suggests, continued support and resources are essential for ensuring that IKS is effectively integrated into the curriculum, creating a learning environment that is both culturally relevant and academically enriching for indigenous students.

Finally, it has been proven that the integration of IKS into Indigenous education programs has profound impacts on students' cultural identity, academic achievement, and overall well-being. By connecting students to their heritage, promoting academic success, and fostering emotional stability, IKS integration creates a holistic educational experience that empowers students and strengthens their sense of self.

Conclusion

The following inferences were made in light of this study's findings:

While there are obstacles such as the need for culturally sensitive materials, language barriers, and resource limitations, opportunities for success lie in community engagement, collaboration with elders, and teacher capacity building.

The integration strategy emphasizes contextualization, cultural sensitivity, and community collaboration, ensuring an education system that is both academically rigorous and culturally relevant, fostering heritage preservation and student success.

Despite facing barriers such as insufficient resources and professional development, teachers demonstrate dedication to integrating IKS authentically, collaborating with indigenous elders, and continually striving for cultural authenticity in their teaching practices.

The incorporation of IKS in education strengthens students' cultural identity, enhances academic performance, and promotes emotional well-being, leading to a well-rounded educational experience that empowers indigenous learners.

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Recommendations

In the light of the findings, the following were recommended:

1. For DepEd, Allocate funds to develop curriculum materials that reflect Indigenous knowledge and traditions, ensuring cultural authenticity and sensitivity, Provide budget allocations for teacher training, language preservation, and community collaboration to overcome resource and personnel challenges, and address language barriers by promoting translation services and resources to accurately represent IKS in both local and mainstream languages.
2. **For School Administrators**, Offer continuous training for teachers to integrate IKS and cultural sensitivity into their teaching practices., Strengthen partnerships with Indigenous communities and elders to ensure cultural relevance and accuracy in curriculum development and teaching, and Allocate time for teachers to collaborate with elders and adjust lesson plans to incorporate IKS effectively.
3. **For Future Researchers**, research successful IKS integration in diverse educational contexts to inform best practices, explore the effectiveness of professional development programs for teachers in integrating IKS, and nvestigate how IKS integration affects students' cultural identity, academic success, and emotional well-being.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to implementation, all of the above plans and suggestions were presented to East-West Mindanao Colleges Inc. to ensure compliance with the procedures. In addition, utilizing Informed Consent Forms (see attachments for forms), the researcher ensured that all collected data were voluntarily supplied by qualified individuals who met the study's inclusion criteria. No one was coerced or recruited into participation (Cerdana & Ngag, 2024).

Participants were interviewed, and focus groups were conducted using validated instruments in settings they perceived to be secure, pleasant, and convenient, with risks minimized or eliminated entirely. Participants had the option of reviewing the collected data. Individuals volunteered their time for interviews lasting thirty (30) minutes to one (1) hour.

The participant's time and effort were recognized by the researcher in the form of a token. Consistent with the Data Privacy Act (DPA), the researcher treated all participant data with the utmost confidentiality, guaranteeing that no identifying information about the study's outcomes would be shared with any third parties.

Informed Consent: Before participation, explicit and informed consent was diligently obtained from all school heads involved in the study. It was imperative that they possessed a comprehensive understanding of the study's objectives, methodologies, potential risks, and benefits. Furthermore, participation remained entirely voluntary, affording participants the autonomy to withdraw from the study at any juncture without encountering any adverse consequences (Dolutan & Ngag, 2024).

Anonymity and Confidentiality: To safeguard the identities and responses of the students, rigorous measures were enacted to ensure anonymity and confidentiality. Rather than using actual names, pseudonyms or codes were employed, upholding the privacy of the

participants. The collected data were securely stored with access restricted solely to the research team.

Avoiding Harm: Delicate subjects, such as the challenges inherent in their roles, were discussed with meticulous consideration for the potential emotional and psychological impact on the participants. Strategies were in place to minimize distress, and a support system was readily available to assist participants should the need arise (Bantillo & Ngag, 2024).

Researcher-Participant Relationship: The researcher maintained a professional and respectful rapport when engaging with the school heads. Any actions that might exploit or cause harm to the participants were scrupulously avoided, ensuring their utmost dignity and respect throughout the research process.

Data Protection: Adherence to data protection regulations and laws was unwaveringly followed to safeguard the personal information of the participants. Stringent measures were employed to ensure the secure storage and transmission of data (Ronquillo, & Ngag, 2024).

Voluntary Participation: Participants were assured that their involvement in the study was wholly voluntary, devoid of any form of coercion or external pressure.

Researcher Bias: The researcher remained vigilant regarding potential biases that might influence data collection and analysis, upholding objectivity and transparency throughout the research endeavor.

Institutional Approval: Before initiating the study, the researcher diligently sought ethical clearance from the pertinent institutional review boards or ethics committees.

Honesty and Integrity: The research findings were reported truthfully and accurately, devoid of any manipulation or distortion to align with preconceived notions or biases.

Beneficence: The potential benefits of the research to educational practices and policies were thoughtfully considered, ensuring that the study positively contributed to the enhancement of the education system.

Cultural Sensitivity: The researcher displayed cultural sensitivity by respecting local customs, beliefs, and practices within the research setting, refraining from imposing external values on the participants.

Inclusion and Diversity: The study's structure prioritized inclusivity and diversity, encompassing a wide spectrum of challenges and opportunities in the integration of traditional wisdom and Indigenous knowledge into the curriculum of Indigenous education programs in Esperanza III, Division of Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2024-2025.

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Declaration AI Tools Declaration

I do hereby declare the use AI tools, such as Chat GPT and Grammarly for grammar checking and sentence organization purposes only.

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